

THE PROCESS OF ESTABLISHING PRESCHOOL INSTITUTIONS IN UZBEKISTAN IN THE LATE 1940s – EARLY 1950s AND EXISTING PROBLEMS

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the development of preschool institutions in Uzbekistan during the period of 1946–1959. The study examines the budgetary funds allocated to the public education sector in the post-war years, the construction of preschool institutions, and issues related to their material and technical support. Based on historical experience, the article highlights the importance of ensuring infrastructure development, adequate financing, and regional balance in improving the modern preschool education system.

At present, the development of the preschool education system in Uzbekistan is considered one of the key priorities of state policy. Expanding the coverage of preschool educational institutions, strengthening their material and technical base, and improving the quality of education and upbringing are at the core of contemporary reforms. The effectiveness of these processes largely depends on a thorough study of the historical experience of the sector's development.

In the post-war years, particularly during 1946–1959, special attention was paid to expanding preschool institutions in Uzbekistan, and the construction of new kindergartens was carried out using funds allocated from the state budget. However, while construction activities intensified mainly in urban areas, problems such as the use of adapted buildings and insufficient material and technical support persisted in rural areas. An analysis of this historical experience is of significant scientific and practical importance for improving mechanisms of balanced regional infrastructure development, planning, and financing in the modern preschool education system.

Between 1946 and 1950, allocations from the State Budget of the Uzbek SSR for the public education sector increased significantly. During these years, a total of 1 billion 32 million soviet rubles was allocated to finance public education, a certain portion of which was directed toward the development of preschool institutions, the construction of new kindergartens, and the repair of existing ones [1.91].

During this period, a number of regulatory documents were developed to promote the development of the preschool education system. In particular, on May 18, 1949, the Central Committee of the All-Union Communist Party (Bolsheviks) and the Council of Ministers of the USSR adopted a resolution "On Measures to Expand Preschool Institutions and Maternity Homes and Improve Their Activities." In order to ensure the implementation of this resolution,

the construction of new types of preschool institutions was launched in Uzbekistan. Such construction was carried out by large organizations, plants and factories, industrial complexes, collective farms (kolkhozes), and state farms (sovkhozes). The buildings were constructed based on the “Construction of Kindergartens and Nurseries” project, as well as special designs developed by the “Uzgosproyekt,” “Uzgioprogor,” and “Uzgiproselstroy” design institutes. Kindergartens built according to these designs were referred to as “standard (typical)” kindergartens. Construction work was implemented by the Ministry of Construction of the Uzbek SSR, the Ministry of Rural Construction of the Uzbek SSR, and the “Boshtoshkentqurilish” organization [5.56.].

While kindergarten buildings in cities were constructed relatively quickly, the situation in rural areas was quite different. In the 1950s, the preschool education system in the Tashkent region, especially in rural areas, was extremely underdeveloped in terms of material and technical resources. Many kindergartens under the jurisdiction of the public education departments operated in adapted buildings originally intended for residential use. For example, Kindergarten №8 under the Qishloq District Department of Public Education of the Tashkent region was located in the territory of the Stalin collective farm of the Voroshilov village council [6.9.]. This institution was organized in an adapted residential building not specifically constructed for children. The floor was wooden, heating was provided by a stove, and due to the kindergarten’s proximity to collective farm stables, sanitary and hygienic conditions did not meet required standards. In Kindergarten No. 1 of the Qishloq district of the Tashkent region, 25 children were enrolled, and the working day lasted 9 hours. The kindergarten had 10 metal beds and 10 folding beds, but other essential equipment was lacking [6.15.].

From 1954 onward, in order to improve the situation, the construction of standard (project-based) buildings was initiated through the efforts of collective and state farms. In that year, 10 new kindergarten buildings were constructed and put into operation in the Tashkent region, while 37 were built in the Andijan region [4.]. However, such developments did not cover all regions of the republic. For instance, in the Kashkadarya region, almost no construction of buildings for kindergartens and nurseries was carried out until 1955, which significantly limited the functioning of preschool institutions [2.95.].

An analysis of the situation across the republic reveals the following. Between January and August 1959, the construction of kindergartens with a total capacity of 16,424 places was planned nationwide. By the end of the year, only 6,624 places had been created in completed buildings, meaning that the plan was fulfilled by only 40 percent. In the same year, projects for the construction of special buildings for nurseries with a capacity of 13,425 places were approved; however, in practice, buildings for only 4,598 places were constructed, resulting in a plan fulfillment rate of just 34 percent [3.68.].

The main reason for such low implementation rates was the untimely delivery of construction materials and necessary resources, as well as supply disruptions, which led to the slowing down and frequent suspension of construction works. This situation negatively affected not only the expansion and modernization of existing childcare institutions but also hindered the achievement of state-defined goals aimed at expanding preschool infrastructure and improving its quality [7.33.].

Conclusion

In 1946–1960, the development of preschool institutions in the Uzbek SSR was one of the important directions of state policy, and measures were taken to finance the sector and construct new kindergartens. The establishment of kindergartens based on standard projects contributed to the expansion of preschool education infrastructure.

However, the incomplete implementation of construction plans, shortages of material and technical resources, and disparities between urban and rural areas limited the development of the preschool education system. This historical experience demonstrates the need, in the present day, to improve mechanisms for balanced regional development of preschool education infrastructure and to enhance financing systems.

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